

Analysis of Information Utilization of Budget Realization on Performance in Regional Government

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ABSTRACT

The budget realization report provides benefits for decisions that will later be accounted for. In government agencies, the performance of users of reports is very important to understand the information on budget realization reports. Where the budget realization report provides information on an overview of the sources, allocations, and use of economic resources managed by the government. This budget realization report is prepared to provide relevant information on the financial position and all transactions carried out by an entity during one period, hereby the performance of the report users must understand the benefits of the budget realization report itself. This study aims to specifically analyze the effect of user performance characteristics on the utilization of budget realization report information. Data were collected from distributing questionnaires to students to understand the performance that should be done in government. Statistical testing was performed using regression analysis using the SPSS 23.0 statistical tool.

1. INTRODUCTION

The accounting process is a series in preparing financial reports, the purpose of financial statements is to provide information regarding the financial position, performance, and changes in the financial position of a company, this information is useful for most users to make decisions (Putra dan Prabowo 2019). Financial reports are also useful for showing the results of management performance against existing resources in the company (Sri Kustono 2021).

In government institutions, financial reports must provide reliable and relevant information about the company's financial position because it is intended to compare how in realizing revenue, expenditure, transfers and financing, as well as all activities that have been

budgeted for (Mulyono 2020). In detail, the purpose of government financial reports is to provide useful information for decision making and show the accountability of the reporting entity (Rakhmayani dan Sudarno 2014).

In article 55 paragraph (5) of Law no. 1 of 2004 concerning the State Treasury which contains the obligation to prepare and submit financial reports including reporting on budget implementation and financial reports that must be submitted to the Minister of Finance, then the Minister of finance submits to the president. Accounting Standards used to prepare government financial reports, namely Government Accounting Standards (SAP) which have been described in government regulation No. 71/2010 (PP RI 2010) this standard is used as a reference in preparing government financial reports, both central and regional.

Within the government agencies themselves, there are several types of reports that must be prepared, one of which is the Budget Realization Report (LRA) where this report aims to provide information on the realization and budget of the reporting entity (Aduroh dan Paramu 2021). Where this information will later be useful for report users in order to reassess decisions about the allocation of economic resources, accountability, and the level of compliance of the reporting entity with the budget (Kustono et al. 2020). This information will also provide information on all details of budget realization in order to assess how the local government is performing regarding the efficiency and effectiveness of the use of reports (Agustin et al. 2021).

The workers (employees) in the government must at least understand how to make use of the budget realization report, so that these employees must understand the financial statements properly so that later when they work they can use them optimally (Ramadhani et al. 2019). There are several factors that influence users in utilizing government financial reports. The influencing factors are the educational background and the user's accounting knowledge (Fontanella 2012) which have an influence on the use of financial statements. These two factors are the most widely used in research. However, this research will also discuss whether gender and social factors will also affect the use of financial reports.

Some of the existing studies discuss what factors can affect user performance on the use of financial statement information and this research is carried out thoroughly on government financial reports (Wijaya et al. 2021). Therefore, in this study specifically analyzed the variables which include the influence of background and level of education, gender, and social factors on the performance of users of budget realization reports.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

A. Budget Realization Report

The budget realization report is a report containing an overview of sources, allocations, and a comparison of the set budget with the realized budget during one reporting period

(Ardianne et al. 2020). This budget realization report shows information on each comparison between realized revenue, expenditure, transfers, and financing with its budget for one period .

a. Revenue-Budget Realization Report (LRA)

Revenue-LRA is obtained from the receipt of the Central / Regional General Treasury Account which will later add to the budget balance during the fiscal year period, the cash will later be received by the State General Treasurer / Regional General Treasurer or by other government entities (Novitasari et al. 2019). This budget will become the right of the government to manage finances and its realization and there is no need for repayment by the government (Taufik et al. 2019).

b. Shopping

Expenditures, namely all required expenditures originating from the State / Regional General Treasury Account which can later reduce the excess budget balance during the implemented budget period for which the government does not receive repayment, the cash is received by the State General Treasurer / Regional General Treasurer (Winarno dan Putra 2020).

c. Transfer

Transfer is an activity related to the receipt or disbursement of money from a reporting entity from or to other reporting entities, including balance funds and profit sharing funds (Jauhar dan Roziq 2019).

d. Financing

The main financing is aimed at covering the deficit or the utilization of the studio surplus (Lee dan Chou 2019). Financing itself is a revenue activity that must be paid back and or expenses that will be received back during the implemented budget period, including the following budget years which are interrelated (Khasanah et al. 2021).

B. Benefits of Information and Relevant Financial Statement Information

The budget realization report provides useful information for users to be able to predict economic resources in funding central or regional government activities in the next period by preparing comparative reports (Novitasari et al. 2019). The budget realization report provides

information to report users regarding indications or indicators of the use of economic resources that have been carried out efficiently, effectively, and economically and in accordance with the previously prepared budget and realized in accordance with statutory regulations described in PP No. 71 (PP RI 2010), There are several main groups of users of government financial reports, but not limited to:

1. Society;
2. People's representatives, supervisory institutions and auditing institutions;
3. Parties who give or play a role in the donation, investment and loan processes; and
4. Government.

In general, the presentation of government financial reporting aims to provide useful information for decision makers (Wijaya et al. 2021). In order to achieve these goals, financial reports must have relevant, reliable, comparable, and understandable characteristics. Information is said (Shoimah et al. 2021).

Relevant if the information contains in it, it can influence the results of users' decisions by helping them to evaluate current or past events, and can be used to predict the future, and can see the results of past evaluations (Jauhar dan Roziq 2019). Relevant has the following criteria:

1. Have benefits from each other (feedback)
2. Has a predictive benefit in the future
3. On time, and;
4. Complete.

C. Education Level and Educational Background

Education level is a measure or a person's achievement in learning. Education level is where there is a level defined based on the level of development of students, the goals to be achieved, and the willingness to be developed (Kustono 2021). Changes in attitude and behavior in healthy life also affect the level of education (Masrohatin dan Tobing 2019). A higher level of education is also considered as being able to make it easier for someone to receive more information and implement it in how someone behaves and their daily lifestyle, especially in health. Formal education forms value for a person, especially in accepting new things according to (Pratiwi 2017).

Education level has certain levels which are differentiated as follows:

a. Initial basic education for 9 years includes SD / equivalent, junior high school / equivalent SD / equivalent education is the most basic level of education (bottom) where at this level of education the beginning of the formation of children's character through formal. SLTP / equivalent education is a level of education above basic education where at this level of education the children are more mature than before.

b. Further education

Secondary education includes SMA / equivalent. This level of education is a continuation of SLTP / equivalent consisting of general secondary education and vocational secondary education such as SMK and SMA.

Higher education includes diploma, bachelor, master, doctoral and specialty. This level of education can be said to be the end of someone who is looking for formal knowledge (Roziq et al. 2020).

Education level and background can be an indicator of human resource competence, where usually a person's job may depend on the level of education and background taken previously such as a job placement in a company that will certainly be placed according to his educational background which can later show optimal performance (Sumani dan Roziq 2020).

D. Gender

The meaning of gender itself is that there is a relationship between biological sex and one's behavior. The term gender means that there are differences between men and women which also contain social values that are closely related to men and women (Winarno dan Putra 2020). Gender is said or associated with positive and negative traits. Basically, men are mostly considered masculinity, while women are more considered femininity, this is later linked to gender roles (Tahar 2012).

Men are mostly seen as more likely to do less in-depth information and only do it in a limited way because this man does not make use of the existing information and the information is not processed as a whole. However, most women

are seen as more likely to carry out more thorough information for decision makers. It is in the cognitive and marketing psychological literature that women are thought to process information more efficiently and effectively for decision making (Sabaruddinsah 2007).

E. Social factors

Basically, a person's behavior can be influenced by the existence of social rules through messages obtained from other people that these people think about and they will practice most of these thoughts (Afandi et al. 2021). In the interpersonal model, Triandis (1980) defines that social factors are internalizing a person from a cultural group and the existence of an agreement between someone who connects other people in certain social situations. Thus from this understanding, social factors can be defined as someone who has influence over the actions of other people who do (ROZIQ et al. 2019).

Thompson et al. (1991) continued research on what social factors can affect the use of information technology. Many of the questions that ask examine social factors in the study, including the number of workers who use information technology, the presence of coworkers and co-workers can encourage someone to use information technology, and organizations can assist in the use of information technology. Thus it can be concluded that social factors can affect the use of personal computers.

Social factors, mostly in previous research associated with the use of information technology. In the use of financial statement information, social factors can prove that an individual can convince himself to use the information or use certain information (Eriandani dan Winarno 2021). This means that there is an influence on the surrounding environment and people around and the organization in using a financial statement information (Lee dan Chou 2019). Encouragement by colleagues, superiors, or organizations can have an influence in the use of financial statement information by an individual.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

a. Type of Research

This type of research uses a quantitative approach where this research is a descriptive and

associative type of research. Where this type of associative research has properties regarding whether there is a relationship or not regarding the research being carried out or this research can also be aimed at seeing the influence between the variables studied. While this type of descriptive research is a part of statistics that studies the tools, techniques, or procedures applied to describe or describe the data set or the results of the observations made (Sugiyono 2010).

b. Data Collection

Data was collected by giving online questionnaires using google form. This questionnaire was distributed to students majoring in accounting in order to find out the opinions of these accounting students. This questionnaire contains questions from each indicator, namely educational background, education level, gender, and social factors. For measuring the answers to the questionnaire, through the use of a five-point Likert scale. The Likert scale is a statement used to ask respondents to answer and to evaluate the level of approval or disagreement (Taufik et al. 2019).

c. Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis technique used in this research is regression analysis which is processed through the SPSS version 23 program (Abdurrasodik et al. 2020). This data analysis technique is used to determine whether there is an influence or not regarding user performance in the utilization of budget realization report information (Putri et al. 2020).

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

a. Validity Test

In testing the validity of this study using the Pearson Product Moment coefficient formulation.

Figure 1. Validity Test

		Correlations		
		X1	X2	X3
X1	Pearson Correlation	1	.715**	.443
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.051
	N	20	20	20
X2	Pearson Correlation	.715**	1	.490*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.028
	N	20	20	20
X3	Pearson Correlation	.443	.490*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.051	.028	
	N	20	20	20

Based on these data, the results of the validity test of the three variables are said to be all valid, because the three variables have a significance value < 0.05 .

b. Reliability Test

The reliability test is a value that shows the consistency of a measuring device in measuring the same symptoms. The Cronbach Alpha value is said to be good if it is between 0.6 to 1.0.

Table 1. Reliability Test

Case Processing Summary		
	N	%
Valid	20	100.0
Cases Excluded ^a	0	.0
Total	20	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.769	3

Based on the reliability test results above, it is known that the Cronbach's Alpha number is 0.769, so it is between 0.6 - 1.0, it can be said that the reliability test of all variables is reliable or reliable.

c. Normality Test

This normality test is carried out to see whether the distribution of the research data for each variable has spread normally or not. According to Hastono (2006), there are 3 ways to measure normality itself, namely:

1. It can be seen from the normal Histogram and Curve graph results. If the shape resembles a Shape bell, it means that the data is normally distributed.
2. Using the Skewness value and the Standard Error. If the Skewness value is divided by the standard error resulting in a number < 2 , then the distribution is normal.
3. The last one is by performing the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test if the test results

are significant ($p \text{ Value} > 0.05$) then the data is normally distributed.

Figure 2. Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		Unstandardized Residual
N		20
Normal Parameters ^{ab}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	1.95119946
	Most Extreme Differences	
	Absolute	.126
	Positive	.075
	Negative	-.126
Test Statistic		.126
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{cd}

Based on the table above, it is known that the significance value of Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) of $0.200 > 0.05$, so in accordance with the basis for decision making in the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test above, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed.

d. Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test is here carried out to determine whether the regression model has a relationship between independent variables. Generally a good regression model should be free from multicollinearity. To detect the presence or absence of multicollinearity, namely in the following ways (Ghozali 2011):

1. First, by knowing or seeing the value of R square (R^2), but most individually the independent variables do not significantly affect the dependent variable.
2. Second, by analyzing the correlation matrix of independent variables. If there is a high enough correlation between the independent variables (more than 0.90), it is an indication of multicollinearity.
3. Finally, by looking at the tolerance value and variance inflation factor (VIF), a regression model that is free of multicollinearity problems if it has a tolerance value of more than 0.1 and a VIF value of less than 10.

Figure 3. Multicollinearity Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	11.489	7.459		1.540	.143		
	pendidikan (x1)	.267	.183	.343	1.460	.164	.478	2.094
	gender (x2)	.479	.227	.511	2.114	.051	.451	2.216
	faktor sosial (x3)	-.112	.293	-.072	-.382	.707	.742	1.347

Based on the data above, all tolerance values are > 0.10. While all VIF values < 10.00, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity symptom in the regression model.

e. Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity Test with Glejser Test. The heteroscedasticity test is intended to test and later find out in the regression model whether there is an inequality of variance from the residuals of one observation to another. However, if the al results remain, it can be called homoscedasticity and if the variance is different it can be called heteroscedasticity.

Figure 4. Heteroscedasticity Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.445	4.282		.571	.576
	pendidikan (x1)	.006	.105	.022	.061	.952
	gender (x2)	.057	.130	.160	.437	.668
	faktor sosial (x3)	-.085	.168	-.145	-.508	.619

Based on the data above, the three independents have a significance value > 0.05, which means there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

f. Multiple Liner Regression analysis test results

Simultant Influence Test / Statistical Test F

The F test is performed to see whether the independent variables together can influence the dependent variable or not. The F test is also used to see whether the regression model used is correct or not. The conditions used in the F test are as follows:

1. If F count is greater than F table or the probability is smaller than the level of significance (significance < 0.05), then the research model can be used or the model is correct.
2. If F count is less than F table or the probability is greater than the level of significance (significance > 0.05), then the research model cannot be used or the model is not correct.

Figure 5. F Test

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	98.864	3	32.955	7.289	.003 ^b
	Residual	72.336	16	4.521		
	Total	171.200	19			

Based on the results of the data above, it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted or in other words all independent variables simultaneously affect the performance of the use of information on budget realization reports because the significance value is < 0.05.

5. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATIONS

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion, several conclusions can be made as follows:

1. The background and level of education have an effect on the user's performance in the utilization of budget realization report information because it has a significance value < 0.05.
2. Gender has an effect on user performance in the utilization of budget realization report information because it has a significance value < 0.05.
3. Social factors have an effect on user performance in the use of budget realization report information because they have a significance value < 0.05.

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